

Stability constants of 5-carboxyuracil and 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil with some metal ions

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Abstract : The stability constants of metal complexes formed between Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , VO^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Fe^{3+} metal ions with 5-carboxyuracil and 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil were determined by potentiometric titration technique. Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration method as modified by Irving-Rossotti was used to calculate the proton-ligand stability constants ($\log K_1^H$, $\log K_2^H$) and metal-ligand stability constants ($\log \beta_n$) values in aqueous, 80 : 20% (v/v) water-ethanol and water-DMSO media at 15 °C temperature and constant ionic strength of 0.1 M NaCl. The correlation between $\log \beta_n$ values and various parameters relating to ligand as well as metal are discussed. The negative ΔG° values indicate that complex formation is spontaneous one.

Keywords : Stability constants, 5-carboxyuracil, 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil, metal ions, dielectric constant.

The importance of pyrimidine derivatives arises from their biological, medicinal and agricultural applications¹ and transition metal complexes of pyrimidines play an important role in the catalysis of drug interactions². Uracil (2,4-dihydropyrimidine) has biological importance in metabolism because some of its derivatives are building blocks for RNA³. The metal complexes of 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil has antitumor⁴ and antimicrobial⁵ activity. The magnesium complexes of 5-carboxyuracil have been reported as potentially useful for magnesium supplementation⁶ while its lithium complexes have been used in lithium therapies⁷. Some work on dissociation constants of pyrimidine derivatives including 5-carboxyuracil⁸ and isolation and characterization of solid complexes of 5-carboxyuracil and 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil has been reported in literature^{9,10} but no work has been done to find the stability constants of their metal complexes in aqueous-organic mixtures. In view of all of the above, it was thought worthwhile to study the complexation equilibria of 5-carboxyuracil and 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil with some transition metal ions. The metal ions used were Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , VO^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Fe^{3+} . The stability constants were determined by using Calvin-Bjerrum potentiometric pH titration technique in aqueous, 80 : 20% (v/v) water-alcohol and 80 : 20% (v/v) water-DMSO media at 15 °C temperature and constant ionic strength of 0.1 M NaCl.

Results and discussion

Proton-ligand stability constants :

The ionization equilibria involved for 5-carboxyuracil

are shown in Scheme 1. The first proton ionization occurs from COOH group ($1 \rightleftharpoons 2$) while second from N_1H or N_3H ($2 \rightleftharpoons 3$). Similarly, the equilibrium for 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil ($4 \rightleftharpoons 6$) can be represented in Scheme 2.

In this case, the first proton ionization occurs from COOH group ($4 \rightleftharpoons 5$). The structure 5 then rearranges¹¹ to structure 6. The second proton is then released from SH group ($6 \rightleftharpoons 7$). The X-ray structural determination of 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil showed it to exist in the lactam-thione form¹². The $\bar{n}_A$ values calculated are in the range of $0 < \bar{n}_A < 2$ for both the ligands. This indicates that there are two protons per ligand molecule. The $\text{p}K_{a1}$ values were calculated by half integral method at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ and 1.5, graphical method from $\log \bar{n}_A/(1 - \bar{n}_A)$ vs pH and $\log (\bar{n}_A - 1)/(2 - \bar{n}_A)$ vs pH, pointwise calculation method, $\log \bar{n}_A/(1 - \bar{n}_A) + \text{pH} = \text{p}K_{a1}$ and $\log (\bar{n}_A - 1)/(2 - \bar{n}_A) + \text{pH} = \text{p}K_{a2}$ and other computational methods¹³. The $\text{p}K_{a1}$ values with error limits ± 0.02

log units are given in Table 1 and there is a good agreement between pK_a values obtained by all the methods.

In the present investigation, the pK_{a1} ($\log K_1^H$) and pK_{a2} ($\log K_2^H$) values are in the order : 5-carboxyuracil > 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil. This indicates the more basic nature of 5-carboxyuracil than its 2-thio derivative. The pK_{a1} and pK_{a2} values (9.12, 4.74; 8.90, 4.43; 8.79, 4.35 for 5-carboxyuracil and 8.00, 4.21; 7.86, 4.07; 7.70, 3.87 for 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil) were observed in water-DMSO, water-ethanol and only water system respectively (Table 1). Higher is the pK_a value, lesser is the tendency to ionize or in other words, lesser acidic character of a particular group. This suggests lesser tendency for ionization in water-DMSO while greater tendency in only water medium. It should be noted that, as predicted by Born equation, the creation of charge in media of low dielectric constants is an unfavourable process and hence resulting in lesser dissociation that is, greater pK_a 's values. Furthermore, for the same (v/v) composition, $\log K^H$ values in different solvent-water mixtures follow the sequence : water-DMSO > water-ethanol which may be explained on the basis of dielectric constant of the solvent-water mixture and proton-solvation properties of the media¹⁴.

Metal-ligand stability constants :

The metal titration curves are well separated from acid and ligand titration curves indicating the formation of metal complexes in solution. The titration studies indicate that complexation initiates from pH 3.8, 3.6, 4.8, 6.3, 5.2 in case of UO_2^{2+} , VO^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Hg^{2+} respectively (aqueous medium) while pH 4.4, 3.8, 4.6, 5.5, 6.5 are the corresponding values in water-ethanol system, and 4.8, 4.8, 6.9, 6.4 and 6.9 in water-DMSO system in case of 5-carboxyuracil. For 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil, the complexation initiates from pH 5.2, 3.9, 4.1, 6.0, 5.5 and 3.7 for Co^{2+} , VO^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} (aqueous medium) while pH 4.8, 3.7, 3.4, 5.1, 4.8 and 3.2 are the corresponding values in water-ethanol system, and 4.3, 3.4, 3.4, 4.6, 5.5 and 3.1 in water-DMSO system. The $\bar{n}$ values lie between 0 and 2 showing thereby the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes in solution except for Fe^{3+} which forms 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes in solution ($\bar{n}$ values lie between 0 and 3). For Fe^{3+} , the complexation initiates at pH 3.2 in aqueous medium, 3.2 in water-ethanol medium and 3.3 in water-DMSO medium. The values of $\log \beta_n$ were calculated by various computational methods¹³ and the values obtained by all these methods (Tables 2 and 3) are in good agreement. The error limits are ± 0.02 log units for $\log \beta_n$ values.

It is evident from the present study that $\log K_1 > \log K_2$ in all the cases. This may be due to weaker interaction of second ligand molecule than the first one. The stability order for different metal ions in case of 5-carboxyuracil was found to be : $UO_2^{2+} > VO^{2+} > Cu^{2+} > Hg^{2+} > Zn^{2+}$ (aqueous only); $UO_2^{2+} > VO^{2+} > Cu^{2+} > Zn^{2+} > Hg^{2+}$ (water-ethanol) and $UO_2^{2+} > VO^{2+} > Zn^{2+} > Cu^{2+} > Hg^{2+}$ (water-DMSO). For 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil the trend : $Fe^{3+} > VO^{2+} > Cu^{2+} > UO_2^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > Zn^{2+} > Co^{2+}$ (water only); $Fe^{3+} > Cu^{2+} > VO^{2+} > UO_2^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > Co^{2+} > Zn^{2+}$ (water-ethanol system) and $Fe^{3+} > Cu^{2+} > VO^{2+} > UO_2^{2+} > Co^{2+} > Zn^{2+} > Ni^{2+}$ (water-DMSO system) was observed. The negative ΔG^0 values (Tables 2 and 3) indicate that the reactions are spontaneous one. A number of attempts have been made to find general relationships which explain the overall stability of a complex.

Table 1. Proton ligand stability constants of 5-carboxyuracil and 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil in aqueous and aqueous-organic mixtures at 15 °C and ionic strength of 0.1 M NaCl

Ligands	Proton-ligand stability constants	Solvent composition (% v/v)		
		Water	Water ethanol (80 20)	Water DMSO (80 20)
5-Carboxyuracil	$\log K_1^H(pK_{a2})$	8.79	8.90	9.12
	$\log K_2^H(pK_{a1})$	4.35	4.43	4.74
5-Carboxy-2-thiouracil	$\log K_1^H(pK_{a2})$	7.70	7.86	8.00
	$\log K_2^H(pK_{a1})$	3.87	4.07	4.21

Table 2. Stability constants of metal complexes with 5-carboxyuracil at temperature 15 °C and $\mu = 0.1$ M NaCl

Solvent composition (% v/v)	Cation	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$	$-\Delta G^0$ (kJ/mol)
Water	Cu^{2+}	6.13	4.69	10.82	59.66
	Zn^{2+}	4.99	4.00	8.99	49.57
	Hg^{2+}	4.88	4.19	9.07	50.01
	UO_2^{2+}	7.78	6.50	14.27	78.69
	VO^{2+}	6.79	5.74	12.53	69.09
Water ethanol (80 20)	Cu^{2+}	6.63	4.63	11.26	62.09
	Zn^{2+}	5.29	4.59	10.18	56.13
	Hg^{2+}	4.74	4.26	9.00	49.63
	UO_2^{2+}	7.13	6.13	13.26	73.12
	VO^{2+}	7.39	5.72	13.11	72.29
Water DMSO (80 20)	Cu^{2+}	4.76	4.08	8.84	48.74
	Zn^{2+}	5.18	4.27	9.45	52.11
	Hg^{2+}	4.70	4.12	8.82	48.63
	UO_2^{2+}	6.68	5.12	11.80	65.07
	VO^{2+}	6.50	4.13	10.63	58.61

Hardness and softness :

The most important generalization about the stability of complexes is that the soft ligand-soft metal ion or hard ligand-hard metal ion complexes are more stable. Based on present values of metal-ligand stability constants i.e. $\log \beta_2$, it was observed that UO_2^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and VO^{2+} complexes of 5-carboxyuracil are more stable than 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil (except VO^{2+} complexes in water-DMSO system). The uracil moiety is an important nucleobase residue in nucleotides and nucleic acids. It offers metal ions the C_2 and C_4 carbonyl oxygens as well as the deprotonated N_3 unit. Carbonyl oxygens are weak coordination sites but, if correctly positioned by a primary site (5-carboxyl group in the present case), they may participate in metal ion coordination¹⁵.

Table 3. Stability constants of metal complexes with 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil at temperature 15 °C and $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M NaCl}$

Solvent composition (% v/v)	Cation	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_3$	$\log \beta_n$	$-\Delta G^\circ$ (kJ/mol)
Water	Cu^{2+}	6.53	5.45	–	11.98	66.06
	Zn^{2+}	3.74	4.14	–	7.88	43.45
	Co^{2+}	4.21	3.44	–	7.65	42.18
	UO_2^{2+}	5.92	5.91	–	11.83	65.23
	VO^{2+}	6.18	5.98	–	12.16	67.05
	Ni^{2+}	4.34	3.62	–	7.96	43.89
	Fe^{3+}	8.10	6.51	5.16	19.77	109.01
Water : ethanol (80 : 20)	Cu^{2+}	7.61	3.69	–	11.30	62.31
	Zn^{2+}	4.30	3.47	–	7.77	42.84
	Co^{2+}	4.42	3.60	–	8.02	44.22
	UO_2^{2+}	6.32	4.94	–	11.26	62.09
	VO^{2+}	6.68	4.60	–	11.28	62.20
	Ni^{2+}	4.79	3.58	–	8.37	46.15
	Fe^{3+}	8.26	6.65	5.25	20.16	111.16
Water : DMSO (80 : 20)	Cu^{2+}	8.57	5.30	–	13.87	76.48
	Zn^{2+}	4.51	3.52	–	8.03	44.28
	Co^{2+}	4.64	3.94	–	8.58	47.31
	UO_2^{2+}	6.45	4.57	–	11.02	60.76
	VO^{2+}	7.34	4.19	–	11.53	63.58
	Ni^{2+}	4.43	2.96	–	7.39	40.75
	Fe^{3+}	8.58	7.82	4.94	21.34	117.67

A comparison of the stability of metal complexes of uracil^{16,17} and 5-carboxyuracil (Table 2) shows that the complexes of the latter are more stable. Thus the binding sites in uracil-5-carboxylic acid towards metal ions are probably the carboxylate anion and the adjacent carbonyl oxygen atom that forms a bidentate scheme which leads to a six membered ring which also finds support from similar reports in literature^{5,8}.

Cu^{2+} complexes of 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil are more stable than 5-carboxyuracil in aqueous, water-ethanol and water-DMSO media. This is also true in uracil and its thio

derivatives. For example, Cu^{2+} complexes of 2-thiouracil are more stable than uracil complexes^{18,19}. It has been reported that metal is bonded to the sulphur atom at 2-position in 2-thiouracil complexes¹⁹. This provides strong evidence for bonding of 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil through S atom to Cu^{2+} in present studies.

Ligand basicity : The ratio of $\log \beta_2 / \sum pK$ for UO_2^{2+} and Zn^{2+} are almost same (except Zn^{2+} in water-ethanol system) indicating thereby the direct correlation of stability of metal complexes with ligand basicity. However, in case of Cu^{2+} and VO^{2+} , the observed higher ratio for 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil complexes (except in water-ethanol system in case of VO^{2+}) indicates the extensive π interaction between metal and ligand²⁰ in each solvent system studied.

Effect of dielectric constant : Co-solvent (DMSO and ethanol in the present case) influences the complexation equilibria in solution due to change in dielectric constant of the medium²¹. The ratios of dielectric constants for various solvents i.e. water/water-ethanol, water/water-DMSO, water-ethanol/water-DMSO and water-DMSO/water-ethanol lie in the range 0.937–1.159 in case of 5-carboxyuracil and 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil. The ratios of $\log \beta_2$ values for the various metal complexes of the above two ligands lie in the range 0.811–1.274. The range of ratios of dielectric constants also fall in this range, thereby indicating that the dielectric constant of the medium is one of the main factor governing the value of $\log \beta_2$ or metal-ligand complex stability.

The effect of solvent on the stabilities of the various complexes was also inferred by plotting $\log \beta_2$ against reciprocal of dielectric constant ($1/\epsilon$). In the present studies, UO_2^{2+} , VO^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Hg^{2+} complexes of 5-carboxyuracil show least $\log \beta_2$ values in water-DMSO medium. DMSO being a dipolar aprotic solvent disrupts the water structure and forms solvent-water complex. The more basic monomeric water molecules in water-DMSO medium compete with the ligands for coordination to metal ions and thus decrease the stability of complexes. Similar behaviour has already been reported in case of dipolar aprotic solvents^{21,22}. The greater solvation of metal ions in DMSO due to its higher polarity than ethanol further accounts for lesser stability of metal complexes²³. Water and ethanol both being protic solvents show almost similar $\log \beta_2$ values in aqueous medium as well as water-ethanol mixture. In case of 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil, Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Fe^{3+} complexes show a peak in $\log \beta_2$ values in water-DMSO medium while it was just the reverse in case of UO_2^{2+} , VO^{2+} and Ni^{2+} complexes.

Experimental

5-Carboxyuracil ($C_5H_4N_2O_4$, M.W. 156.1) and 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil ($C_5H_4N_2O_3S$, M.W. 172.2) were procured from M/s. Sigma-Aldrich Chemical Co., St. Louis, MO, USA. All other reagents used were of analar grade.

5-Carboxyuracil solution (0.004 M), 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil solution (0.0033 M) and solutions of various metal salts (0.004 M) were prepared by dissolving their required quantities in doubly distilled water.

A 'Digital pH meter' Model 5652 A (Electronic Corporation of India Limited) with glass and calomel electrodes assembly, reading upto 0.01 units was used for measuring the pH of solutions prepared. Before starting the experiment, the pH meter was standardized with the help of buffer solutions of pH 4.0, 7.0 and 9.2.

Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti²⁴ was used for potentiometric determination of proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants. The experimental procedure involves three sets of titrations which are (i) mineral acid alone, (ii) mineral acid + ligand, (iii) mineral acid + ligand + metal ion. For 5-carboxyuracil (i) 1 ml 0.02 N HCl + 2 ml 1 M NaCl + 17 ml water; (ii) 1 ml 0.02 N HCl + 2 ml 1 M NaCl + 5 ml 0.004 M 5-carboxyuracil solution + 12 ml water; (iii) 1 ml 0.02 N HCl + 2 ml 1 M NaCl + 5 ml 0.004 M 5-carboxyuracil solution + 1 ml 0.004 M metal solution + 11 ml water mixtures were prepared for these titrations. In case of 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil (i) 1 ml 0.02 N HCl + 2 ml 1 M NaCl + 17 ml water; (ii) 1 ml 0.02 N HCl + 2 ml 1 M NaCl + 10 ml 0.0033 M 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil solution + 7 ml water; (iii) 1 ml 0.02 N HCl + 2 ml 1 M NaCl + 10 ml 0.0033 M 5-carboxy-2-thiouracil solution + 1.5 ml 0.004 M metal solution + 5.5 ml water mixtures were prepared for these titrations.

Similarly, above titrations were performed in aqueous-organic media (80 : 20% v/v water-ethanol and 80 : 20% v/v water-DMSO) separately. The pH meter readings in aqueous-organic mixtures were corrected²⁵. These sets were titrated independently against standard NaOH (prepared in aqueous only or 80 : 20% v/v aqueous-organic solvent) solution and at temperature of 15 °C and ionic strength of 0.1 M NaCl.

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